

Carmen Palmer. *Converts in the Dead Sea Scrolls: The Gēr and Mutable Ethnicity*. STDJ 126. Leiden: Brill, 2018. Hardback. 231 pages. \$126.00. ISBN 9789004378179.

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Converts in the Dead Sea Scrolls: The Gēr and Mutable Ethnicity, seeks to reconsider the meaning of the term *gēr* when it appears within the Dead Sea Scrolls. The term itself, a scriptural term denoting a “resident alien,” undergoes a significant sociohistorical shift within the rabbinic period to denote a “Gentile convert to Judaism.” The aim of this study is to examine the usage of the term in the Qumran corpus vis-à-vis how the term is employed within the Hebrew Bible. The goal of such a study is to illuminate what the term *gēr* specifically denotes within the Dead Sea Scrolls and what this might tell us about the Qumran movement’s thoughts on matters of inclusion and exclusion. In the end, Palmer concludes that the term *gēr* *does* indeed denote a “Gentile convert” within the Scrolls, but importantly, the Scrolls do not, as argued by some, present a singular, negative attitude towards the *gēr*.

Palmer begins her study with an introductory chapter providing an overview of contemporary scholarship on the utilization of *gēr* in the biblical tradition and the Dead Sea Scrolls. Regarding the latter, Palmer notes that while there is no unified opinion on the meaning of the term in the Scrolls, the overall scholarly assumption is that the term *does not* refer to a “Gentile convert” given the socially closed nature of the Qumran movement. Palmer concludes the first chapter by outlining her understanding of key theoretical terms, such as “ethnicity” and “conversion,” along with the methodological underpinnings of the study.

In chapter 2, Palmer takes a preliminary step by examining the provenance and dating of the Dead Sea Scroll texts in which the term *gēr* is either preserved or reconstructed. Paleography, orthography, and various literary devices (thematic, historical, and literary allusions) are utilized to determine whether the texts can be connected to the Qumran movement as well as how they correlate with the *Damascus Document* (D) and the *Community Rule* (S), which Palmer determines to be two separate traditions within the Qumran movement. Here, texts are categorized as: (1) those texts influencing the D and S traditions; (2) those correlating with the D tradition; (3) those correlating with the S tradition; and (4) those whose correlation with the D or S tradition is indeterminate.

Chapter 3 compares the utilization of the term *gēr* within Scrolls texts that engage in “scriptural rewriting,” or as Palmer puts it, “a recognizable reuse of scripture” (p. 93) vis-à-vis their scriptural antecedent. Here, Palmer carefully observes the changes made between the “rewriting” and the antecedent concluding that the Scrolls demonstrate a change in meaning away from “resident alien” and towards a “Gentile convert.” For Palmer, this change provides supporting evidence for the mutability of identity within Hellenism and Second Temple Judaism. Palmer further asserts that while *gēr* represents a Judean convert in the Scrolls, there are marked differences in attitude between the D and S traditions regarding inclusion and exclusion. In short, while the D tradition is inclusive of the *gēr* as full member of the Qumran movement, the S tradition is exclusionary.

Chapter 4 closely analyzes three central features of ethnic identity: the shared notion of kinship, connection to land, and common culture (specifically the ritual of circumcision). Palmer finds that the *gēr*’s identification as a non-blood related “brother” supports the notion of mutable

identity within the Qumran movement. Moreover, the *gēr* is included in texts which address connection to the land. Regarding circumcision, Palmer concludes that while the ritual is not explicitly connected with the *gēr* in either the D or S tradition, there are references to circumcision in CD 16:4–6 and 4Q266 6 ii 6 as well as to a metaphorical and spiritual “circumcision” in texts Palmer associates with the S tradition (1QpHab 11:12–13; 4QCatenaA 9 8; 1QS 5:4–5). For Palmer, this metaphorical and spiritual “circumcision” in the S tradition is significant in that it connotes a transformation to a kind of “supra-Judaism,” a form of Judaism to which the *gēr* is excluded.

Chapter 5 offers a sociohistorical comparison of the element of “brotherhood” within the Qumran movement to the “brother” language found in Greco-Roman professional and cultic associations. Palmer concludes that the language of brotherhood among group members, especially that of the formal title “Adopted Brothers” in cultic associations of the Bosphorus region, reflects a notion of shared kinship that bonds members into a shared identity. The implication is that a disparate group can attain a group-specific and socially constructed sense of shared kinship. For Palmer, this supports the proposal that the *gēr* can attain a shared kinship and consequently a shared ethnicity with other members within the Qumran movement.

Palmer’s argument is innovative and discerning. A word of refinement is in order, however. Palmer’s distinction between the D and S tradition regarding converts requires a bit more nuance. In speaking about the community, 1QS 5:6 states, “They shall atone for all those who are fervently committed to holiness in Aaron and for the house of truth in Israel *as well as those who join them as a community*” (cf. 4Q256 9 6 // 4Q258 1 5, trans. Hempel, italics my own). This seems to hint of an openness to converts to the Qumran movement in the S tradition. Palmer reads this as referring to a conversion to “supra-Judaism” by those of the S tradition themselves (p. 153), but this is not altogether clear. The phrase could potentially refer to a *gēr*.

This refinement notwithstanding, there is much to commend in Palmer’s book. The study is focused and carefully constructed, bringing past scholarly engagement regarding the term *gēr* into new focus alongside the current discussion. Texts in the Qumran corpus are judiciously analyzed and are astutely placed in conversation with one another and with their scriptural antecedents. The result is a study which advances our understanding of identity and ethnicity in the Second Temple period.

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